

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP4 – Technical Implementations

D4.4 Report on educational and training material for the developed analytical tools

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Development - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland
Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The EHDEN Project aspires to educate, via the EHDEN Academy, project colleagues and all relevant external stakeholders within Europe (and beyond), in particular the wider OHDSI global network as a key collaboration community supporting this. It is noteworthy that such bodies as the European Medicines Agency, and the European Commission itself highlight the need for upskilling in this domain and the opportunity for educational resources.

Initially, the aim was to train selected Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) selected through our open call process to ensure a consistent methodology for the mapping (ETL) of Data Partner source data to the OMOP common data model. This has led to the establishment of the EHDEN Academy, a Moodle-based, open-source platform. Six modules were created in 2019 as a basis for the initial curriculum and learning path, focused on SMEs. However, these courses are also of great value for others in the community.

The EHDEN Academy has been successfully used in training the 26 SMEs in the first two open calls, and more will be trained in further calls over the duration of the EHDEN project.

To enhance the project's offering, the educational content was launched publicly on 23rd April 2020 with a plan to expand the courses and material for a wider audience, inclusive of Data Partners, researchers, regulators, HTA bodies, and anyone conducting observational research. Additional courses are being produced and content expanded.

Uptake of the Academy has been positive, and the curriculum will be widened with learning paths and modules through the remainder of 2020 and beyond to support observational health research on a wider scale. An Executive Board, Project Management Team and Faculty have been established to operate the Academy, with representation from Academic and EFPIA partners, as well as OHDSI colleagues.

A sustainability plan for the Academy is being developed, focusing on scenarios for community expansion and financial scenarios for independent continuance alongside the EHDEN project.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable describes the educational output of EHDEN to date, specifically related to the programme to support Small and Medium-sized (SME) training and certification via the Extract, Transform and Load (ETL) learning pathway. In addition this work supports EHDEN Data Partners, project Partners and research colleagues.

For the project, based on survey work conducted with the project Partners by WP6 in evaluating various sustainable value propositions, education was seen as an important co-proposition. It in combination with the majority of other possible options for sustainability for the EHDEN project.

In particular, the development and launch of the EHDEN Academy, a free online educational resource open to all working in observational research, has been a major milestone of the project and will be expanded further to multiple learning paths in collaboration with OHDSI for the remainder of the project. We expect the Academy to evolve into an important, collaboratively maintained resource for all those who are engaged with observational research utilising the OHDSI framework, OMOP common data model (CDM) and standardised analytical pipelines.

2. DEVELOPMENT OF THE EHDEN ACADEMY FOR SME EDUCATION IN EUROPE

The initial priority for the EHDEN project was to train and certify SMEs who would be selected through our open calls to support Data Partners mapping their data to the OMOP CDM.

2.1 During year one of the project the following steps were taken to respond to this need:

- An ETL curriculum was created which incorporates key learning modules to ensure a consistent approach to the mapping of Data Partner data, supporting the project’s remit of certification of said SMEs prior to being able to assist with this process.
- The open source, online course management system, Moodle, was decided to be the most user-friendly platform for which to host the curriculum, as well as forming the foundation for future expansion. Modules were created *de novo* by collating new and existing video lectures from the OHDSI community, with additional text, images, and other materials where relevant.
- A course development guide was created for faculty and module developers. It describes the underlying philosophy, knowledge checker guidelines and specific material management (see Annex 1).
 - An instructional systems design was applied incorporating Bloom’s taxonomy for outcomes-based education.
 - Intrinsic to the approach was the utilisation of the ADDIE model, incorporating:
 - Analysis: what is the basis for this education, are all factors evaluated and understood?
 - Design: a rational blueprint with clear objectives
 - Development: course material creation aligned to the analysis and design outputs
 - Implementation: internal testing and course provision
 - Evaluation: continuous feedback loops and responses
- Modules were identified to be incorporated for the initial SME learning path, with two introductory modules and four focused on relevant tools:
 - Overview of the Project

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- Overview of the Curriculum
- OMOP CDM and Standardised Vocabularies
- Infrastructure
- Extract, Transform and Load
- OHDSI-in-a-box
- Further details on these modules follow:
 - **EHDEN Academy: Getting Started**
 - This course gives a brief introduction to the EHDEN Academy and its key features.
 - The estimated time for course completion is 15 minutes.
 - **EHDEN Foundation**
 - The aim of the EHDEN foundation course is to explain what the EHDEN project aims to achieve and how it will accomplish. However, no project stands alone and therefore we provide context on how EU research is being done, why real world evidence is important and about our collaboration with OHDSI.
 - While this course is written from a non-technical, managerial point of view, the context it provides is important to understand what drives EHDEN and why EHDEN works the way it does.
 - The estimated time for course completion is 30 minutes.
 - **OMOP CDM and Standardised Vocabularies**
 - This course is based on the OMOP CDM and Standardised Vocabularies workshop offered by OHDSI at the annual symposium in 2018 and is further extended for use by EHDEN. The course gives an introduction into the history of the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) and the birth of Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI). It highlights OHDSI's vision as well as how OHDSI is trying to drive the future of observational research through network studies. This introduction serves as the basis for the rest of the course's material.
 - The course then moves on to explaining the OMOP Vocabularies, as it is important to understand how the vocabulary is used in examples prior to moving on to the OMOP CDM. The final section of the course explains in detail the layout of the CDM as well as some key concepts such as era logic.
 - The course contains exercises to test understanding and it recommends how to use OHDSI-in-a-Box to go along with these exercises.
 - The estimated time for course completion is 7 hours.
 - **Infrastructure**
 - This course describes the infrastructure and tools used to work with patient-level data converted to the OMOP CDM. Within this course we cover the process for installing and configuring the OHDSI's WebAPI and ATLAS tools. OHDSI's WebAPI is a Java-based application that provides a web-based application programming interface (API) for standardized analytics against one or more OMOP CDMs. Next, we install the OHDSI ATLAS web application and configure it to use WebAPI. ATLAS is used to design and execute observational analyses against the OMOP CDM.
 - This course also covers the installation of R and RStudio and how to use some of the OHDSI R libraries for designing database queries against the OMOP CDM.
 - The course contains video lectures that walk through the setup of the tools on a virtual Windows Server. An OHDSI-Install-Server virtual machine for this course is

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provided and is used for the exercises in the course (for more information please refer to the course resources and the OHDSI-in-a-Box course).

- The estimated time for course completion is 2 and a half hours.
- **Extract, Transform and Load**
 - This course describes Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) processes to take a database from raw observational data to the OMOP Common Data Model. Steps one and two will focus on the tools available for designing ETL logic in a way to communicate to a developer how source data should be handled during conversion to the OMOP Common Data Model. This includes discussion of practical methods for mapping source vocabulary values to Standard OMOP Concepts and a demonstration of how to handle situations where pre-specified mappings do not exist. Steps three and four go over some examples and guidelines when it comes to implementing and testing the ETL logic.
 - The estimated time for course completion is 5 hours.
- **OHDSI-in-a-box**
 - In this course we teach how to quickly deploy OHDSI-in-a-Box, which is a single instance implementation of OHDSI tools and sample data for personal learning and training environments. OHDSI-in-a-Box contains SynPUF data (a synthetic dataset) in OMOP CDM, an RDBS including query client, WebAPI, ATLAS, R and Python. The OHDSI-in-a-box VM is used in other courses, such as the CMD and Standardised Vocabularies, for exercises.
 - In the end of the course we optionally introduce OHDSI on AWS, which is an enterprise class, multi-user, scalable and fault tolerant OHDSI environment on AWS.
 - Estimated course completion is 90 minutes.
- **ATLAS (launched beyond the initial ETL learning path)**
 - This course launched at the time of writing as part of the course content development (see later), and was not core the ETL learning pathway, but will be added to it and other learning paths
 - ATLAS is a free, publicly available web-based, open-source software application developed by the OHDSI community to support the design and execution of observational analyses to generate real world evidence from patient level observational data. ATLAS can be installed locally within your institution to perform analyses across one or more observational databases which have been standardised to the OMOP Common Data Model and can facilitate exchange of analysis designs with any other organisations across the OHDSI community who have adopted the same open science community standards and tools. This course is based on ATLAS version 2.7.
 - The course covers Data Sources, Search, Concept Tests, Cohort Definitions, Characterisation, Cohort Pathways, Incidence Rates, Profiles, Estimation and Prediction
 - Estimated course completion is 3 and a half hours.
- All courses contain knowledge checkers where relevant to evaluate participant progress and understanding.
- For SMEs seeking certification, the online modules needed to be completed by all relevant personnel in the selected SMEs and were complemented via an in-person two-day course

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held at EMC to further reinforce salient content and learning, as well as to evaluate each SMEs ability to map synthetic data to the OMOP CDM. SMEs were also afforded some time to discuss the relevance to their business, plans of engagement within EHDEN and OHDSI and to discuss next steps in e.g. working with Data Partners.

2.2 Outcome of Year One

During the first year of EHDEN (November 2018 – December 2019) eleven SMEs completed the online course and two-day certification meeting in two cohorts, ready to work with Data Partners from the first and prospective open calls. We also invited each SME to provide feedback on the process, the curriculum content and certification meeting, allowing us to enhance this for subsequent SMEs selected in future calls. Overall, the response was very positive, with no significant concerns expressed, but useful and constructive feedback to improve the curriculum content was received. At the time of writing, a second cohort of 15 SMEs are progressing through training and certification following an open call in February 2020.

The OHDSI community also published the Book of OHDSI, which is maintained on GitHub in an electronic, updateable format, and also published in paperback. The Book of OHDSI, which includes major contributions from some EHDEN partners, is a useful complement to the EHDEN academy so the electronic version is mentioned on the Moodle platform and a paperback copy was provided to SMEs undergoing certification.

3. PROJECT LAUNCH OF THE EHDEN ACADEMY (AND BEYOND YEAR ONE)

Figure 1: EHDEN Academy Home Page (<http://academy.ehden.eu>)

The project always envisaged the need to provide educational support beyond the SME training and certification programme, inclusive of Data Partners, data scientists, epidemiologists, statisticians, bioinformaticians, et al. Such a need for upskilling in this domain has already been well recognised by many, including the European Medicines Agency, and the EU Commission itself.

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Following the feedback received by the first SMEs in 2019, the content and platform were improved, and the Academy site on Moodle was further enhanced with relevant branding and identifiable EHDEN ‘look and feel’.

The EHDEN Academy was publicly launched on April 23rd, 2020 (coincident with International Book Day) via the project’s multiple media channels.

The EHDEN Academy has been created as the online educational resource for anyone working in the domain of real world data and real world evidence. Originating in the project, its goal is to build upon the foundations of that project and its collaboration with the OHDSI project, developing richer content for an expanding audience.

3.1 Mission and Vision of the Academy

The EHDEN Academy aims to be a resource for all those who generate and utilise real-world data, work technically with it (e.g. ETL and mapping), and are involved in methodological development and the use of standardised analytical tools.

The EHDEN Academy’s mission is to provide quality education for the open science community at scale, supporting our greater vision within EHDEN of ensuring 21st century tools for 21st century research that ultimately improve treatment for patients across Europe.

The EHDEN Academy is not an educational institution, and does not issue certifications, but strives to provide high quality, open science educational resources. Future opportunity could be a more formalised educational entity, but this is to be evaluated.

3.2 Organisation of the Academy:

- In the lead up to the launch, an Executive Board was established including colleagues from the EHDEN Public and EFPIA partners, OHDSI, and IQVIA, all of whom are involved significantly within education in this domain. The Board is led by a nominated Director, the EHDEN Project Lead for the duration of the project.
- For operational oversight and implementation, a Project Management Team (PMT) was set up, including academic and project management colleagues from Public and EFPIA partners. The PMT is tasked with managing and maintaining the Moodle platform, facilitating content expansion, supporting the Faculty, and promoting and communicating on the Academy.
- A Faculty has been established including EHDEN and OHDSI colleagues to generate new content. The Faculty will be expanded to ensure course content can be generated, but also self-evaluated (i.e. through multiple choice questions and other exercises) and to support the participants with specific educational or technical issues.

3.3 Uptake and course utilisation:

- At time of writing there are 301 users, with ~50% being active in the last two weeks
- Major concentration in US, UK and Spain, but an international distribution.
- The course experience reflected our focus on training SMEs, with all current modules expected to be completed by each of the 26 SMEs to date.
- For the six courses, between 72 to 131 participants have enrolled, with an average of 46% completion at this moment. Many participants have enrolled for certification through the ongoing EHDEN SME calls, but others have also enrolled via promotion. The OMOP CDM course has attracted the most participants.

Figure 2: Global distribution of initial participants following launch

Figure 3: European distribution of initial participants following launch

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Figure 4: Introductory Courses on the EHDEN Academy

Figure 5: Most active course by time versus views/posts in each course

Figure 6: Most active course by participants

4. EXPANDING THE EHDEN ACADEMY

4.1 Content expansion

- Reinforcing the current ETL learning path which supports SMEs with additional content to enhance their work with Data Partners.
- Development of additional learning paths for varied roles, from researchers to regulators, and Data Partners.
- Teaching modules for tools, methods, data sources and additional contextual material
- Linkage to the ever widening OHDSI content and community.
- Current planning is for key content to be generated prior to end 2020, and this has been initiated by the launch of the course on the ATLAS tool.

Figure 7: ATLAS Course content

Figure 8: Expansion plan for course content and modules

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Figure 9: Learning Pathways and Module Content

4.2 Community expansion:

- Content is the main output from the Academy, which drives interest to participate and to be educated. Of note, key stakeholders in the domain of using observational data, such as the European Medicines Agency including its associated European national drug agencies (HMA EMA Big Data Taskforce Report, January 2020, point to the need to upskill their workforces to facilitate research at scale). This has also been noted by the EU Commission itself with respect to e.g. the European Health Data Space.
- Meanwhile, we continue to promote the Academy via our usual social networks and channels as an educational platform to relevant audiences for the EHDEN project, as well as in the observational research domain.
- Of particular note the EHDEN Academy could also be a resource for sister BD4BO projects to support their own projects, their personnel and particular goals, such as ETL of their own Data Partners.
- A communication plan post-launch of the Academy has been developed, in parallel with the project plan, as well as the content development and sustainability plan.

- **Strategic:**
 - Promotion of quality standards in observational research
 - Provision of educational resources globally
 - Linkage with OHDSI community
- **Tactical:**
 - Launch of Learning Paths, modules and content – curriculum development
 - Insights derived from participant community
 - Also linked to EHDEN's/OHDSI's communication activities

July	August	September	October	November	December
Updates on Course Content		Updates on Course Content	OHDSI Forum	Updates on Course Content	
Faculty	Faculty	Faculty	Faculty	Faculty	Faculty
Forum	Forum	Forum	Forum	Forum	Forum
			Promotion	Promotion	Promotion
	Participant Feedback		Participant Feedback		Participant Feedback
			2021 Planning		
			Financial Sustainability Plan	Financial Sustainability Plan	Financial Sustainability Plan

- It will be important to ensure current and future participants can see course creation and delivery
- Feedback on the Academy will be an important component of directing content strategy, as well as communications
- Impact from funding/sponsorship decisions (see later) TBD

Figure 10: Communications plan for remainder of 2020

4.2 Educational focus and sustainability:

- Critical to future success will be the quality of both the educational content, and the evaluation of educational impact, allied to a longer term sustainability beyond the confines of the EHDEN project itself.
- An interim and longer term sustainability plan is being developed for the remainder of the IMI project and beyond, inclusive of various scenarios and funding options via WP6 (as referred to in the introduction).

The EHDEN Academy's mission is to provide quality education for the open science community at scale, supporting our greater vision within EHDEN of ensuring 21st century tools for 21st century research that ultimately improve treatment for patients across Europe

- Free to participants via the Moodle online platform
- Content provision from OHDSI and EHDEN for quality course material
- Extension of the OHDSI community and crowdsourced education
- Learning path development to support varied roles in conducting observational research
- Standards communication for consistency in observational research quality
- Sustainable platform (status to be considered)

Figure 11: EHDEN Academy vision goals

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5. CONCLUSION

A key role of EHDEN from its inception is to educate in the domain of observational research, supporting critical aspects of the project, such as training SMEs in a consistent methodology in ETL to the OMOP CDM with Data Partners. The aspiration, via the now established Academy, is to support education of anyone involved in conducting observational research with requisite interest in methods, tools and data sources.

Alongside the wider OHDSI community, there is an opportunity to enhance and improve quality standards by providing standardised educational content and promoting consistency and quality in utilising real world data, initially via EHDEN, but also internationally via the global OHDSI network.

The project will be instituting a sustainability plan for the Academy independent of the project itself, ultimately as a ‘spin off’ from the project, but closely allied to the its goals, ensuring it has a financial plan to sustain it as a continuing, free for use, educational platform.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1: The EHDEN Academy – Course Development Guideline

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The EHDEN Academy: Course Development Guideline

P.Rijnbeek

05/05/2019

Version 1.0

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INTRODUCTION

There is a clear need for education and training in the eco-system we are building, it is crucial for its adoption and sustainability. In EHDEN we are therefore committed to develop the EHDEN Academy, an online e-learning platform that covers all important topics in the journey from source health data to reliable evidence generation.

The EHDEN Academy is an activity that will last for the enter project lifetime and should result in a sustainable learning environment post EHDEN project. Initially the focus is on the learning path for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), but we will expand to other stakeholders, e.g. data partners, regulators, OHDSI Community in general.

We will develop the Academy using an agile approach in which we start with the following courses (list may change based on ongoing discussions):

1. EHDEN Foundational.

This course will provide the basic information about the EHDEN project, IMI, Federated Networks and Data Privacy basics, high-level introduction to OHDSI.

2. OMOP Standardized Vocabularies and Common Data Model

This course will improve the understanding of the OMOP Vocabularies and will then explain in detail the layout of the CDM as well as some key concepts such as era logic

3. Extraction Transform and Load

Here all the steps from source data to CDM are explained, e.g., the use of the supportive tools in this process, and approaches to assess the validity of the transformation

4. OHDSI Tools

In this course an overview is provided of the tools in the eco-system to perform reliable and reproducible research in the federated data network. The focus is on the ATLAS tool and its components.

These courses will be phased in for the Pilot SMEs, i.e. more courses will become available over time. It is crucial we involve the Pilot SMEs in further optimizing the courses and therefore need to build in multiple evaluation steps.

This document is intended to prove a framework for the course development in the EHDEN Academy. The information is obtained from online material and educational research resources (sometimes verbatim). It starts by briefly describing the Instructional Systems Design (ISD) approach which is a proven methodology to the development of course material. After that we will provide guidance on the creation of tests for the courses.

INSTRUCTIONAL SYSTEMS DESIGN

Instructional Systems Design (ISD) is a popular and proven framework for the development of instructional courses. It describes a number of empirically tested approaches that will help us to move progress towards a powerful and very valuable blended learning environment. ISD is a general framework for designing instructional systems and is not only applicable to e-learning. It is underpinned by theoretical and conceptual components developed by a large number of people in the education and psychology domain.

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Bloom’s taxonomy

Bloom is often called the father of outcome-based education and it describes hierarchical stages that reflect learner progress from novice to expert. The Figure below shows the taxonomy which is a key building block in ISD. It helps teachers teach and students learn.

Figure 1. Bloom’s taxonomy (image courtesy of fractus learning)

The ADDIE Model

The Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation (ADDIE) model currently is a gold standard in the ISD process. ADDIE is often miss-understood as to be performed in a linear pattern of steps but in practice there are multiple iterations of all or some of the steps. Below a brief explanation is provided for each step.

Analysis

This should be the first step in any course design but is often skipped. Here you need to frame the challenge “Why do I actually need to teach this?”, “Will the course solve the problem?”, “Do I have the knowledge experts to build the course”, “Are the timeliness feasible”?

Design

You have to spend a proper amount of time on building a blueprint for the course. This should contain: Rationale, Objectives, Population Profile, Course Description, Learner and Facilitator prerequisites, Evaluation Strategy, Deliverables. The creation of well-defined objectives is an important step and is therefore explained in more detail in the next section.

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Development

In the development phase we create all the course material, i.e. lectures, assessment test etc. This can contain already available material from OHDSI training we make more accessible through the EHDEN academy. Defining the units of instruction (or module, lesson, chapter) requires you to able a chunking method in which you divide the total content in pieces that require similar information or skills. In general, it is better to divide the course into smaller pieces and avoid long lectures (max 45 min). Alternatively, small video snippets (couple of minutes) followed by a test might work well.

Implementation

In this step the course is tested in practice by the trainees and all content is delivered. In EHDEN we foresee internal testing and external testing by the Pilot SMEs.

Evaluation

Even though this is the last letter in the ADDIE acronym it does not mean you do not have to evaluated earlier as well. There is however a lot of value in testing the mastery of the topics by evaluating the course later in time. In EDHEN this can be based on how well the SMEs are able to actually perform the learned tasks in practice. This will inform us on how to further improve the training material.

Developing Objectives

It is crucial to define observable and measurable objectives for the course. We need to be able to understand what it is we are training, and we need to be able to test if we achieve that goal. It is often tempting to have an objective that says something like: “The trainee will be able to understand how the Standardized Vocabularies work.”. It is however unclear how we can test their understanding. Fortunately, there are frameworks that provide guidance in writing objectives. The A-B-C-D Format, i.e. Audience, Behaviour, Condition, Degree, developed by Henich, et al. This four-part plan makes the job of writing objectives easier because you can first focus on each element.

- Audience – learners for whom the objective is written;
- Behaviour – the verb that describes what the audience will be able to do (e.g., describe, explain, find, communicate);
- Condition – the circumstances under which the audience will perform the behaviour (e.g., when a learner obtains medicine from the pharmacy s/he will be able to read the dosage);
- Degree – acceptable performance of the behaviour (i.e., how well the learner performs the behaviour).

The objective does not have to be written in this order (ABCD), but it should contain all of these elements

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Bloom et al created a list of verbs to use for the different levels that could be useful:

KNOWLEDGE	COMPREHENSION	APPLICATION
Cite	Associate	Apply
Count	Classify	Calculate
Define	Compare	Complete
Draw	Compute	Demonstrate
Identify	Contrast	Employ
Indicate	Describe	Examine
List	Differentiate	Illustrate
Name	Distinguish	Interpret
Point	Estimate	Locate
Quote	Explain	Operate
Read	Express	Order
Recite	Extrapolate	Predict
Record	Interpret	Practice
Relate	Interpolate	Relate
Repeat	Locate	Report
Select	Predict	Restate
State	Report	Review
Tabulate	Restate	Schedule
Tell	Review	Solve
Trace	Sketch	Translate
Write	Translate	Utilize
ANALYSIS	SYNTHESIS	EVALUATION
Analyze	Arrange	Appraise
Appraise	Assemble	Assess
Contrast	Collect	Choose
Criticize	Compose	Critique
Debate	Construct	Determine
Detect	Create	Estimate
Diagram	Design	Evaluate
Differentiate	Detect	Grade
Distinguish	Formulate	Judge
Experiment	Integrate	Measure
Infer	Organize	Rank
Inspect	Plan	Rate
Inventory	Prepare	Recommend
Question	Prescribe	Revise
Separate	Produce	Score
Summarize	Propose	Select
	Specify	Test

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There are two different types of objectives: terminal and enabling. A terminal objective is the final (exit) competency expected of the learner, it is a written statement of the sum of all the enabling objectives and precedes the enabling objectives. The enabling objectives break down the terminal objective to its most basic learning objectives.

DEVELOPING TESTS

In the design phase of the course curriculum of the EHDEN Academy we have to develop tests and this section provides some guidance on writing tests based on empirical evidence mainly from the field of psychometrics. This field studies the science of measurement of mental types of characteristics, like knowledge, skills and abilities, and tries to create and use scales for their assessment.

What makes a good test?

It might sound as an open door, but a test should measure what it claims to measure, and it needs to be reliable. You have to decide before writing tests what you aim to measure, in enough detail. **Reliability** refers to the fact that assessment tools produce repeatable and consistent information about a person's knowledge, skill and abilities. There are different ways of obtaining reliability estimates of tests, e.g. by comparing the scores of students over time. Another important measure is Validity. **Validity** is the extent to which evidence supports our interpretations and uses of the test. In other words, it refers to what characteristic the test measures and how well the test measures that characteristic. This implies that the validity of a test is an ongoing and continuous characteristic, a test is neither validated nor invalidated. Validation is the gathering of the evidence to support interpretation and score use in a specific context. We need to make sure the test clearly represents the important instructional and learning goals and objectives, and so we can support our claims about what students now and can do as a result of their test performance. It indicates the usefulness of the test.

Writing multiple choice questions

Writing good multiple-choice questions is not as easy as it may sound. The way we write the question and the answer items is critical to make the test reliable and valid. Each of the items is a building block of the test and there is important advice from the education research field we should consider that have been obtained from empirical evidence.

A multiple-choice question originates from a **stimulus**, which is the contextual information relevant to the item. The multiple-choice question itself consists of two standard parts: a problem (stem) and a list of suggestions solutions (options). The **stem** is best written in the form of a complete question or statement. The list of **options** contains one correct or best option (**answer**) and a number of incorrect or inferior options (**distractors**).

Write questions that match the topics in each content domain and pay particular attention to writing questions that cover the range of the three cognitive domains: the applying and reasoning domains, as well as the knowing domain.

Item writing is a task that requires imagination and creativity, but at the same time demands considerable discipline in working within the assessment frameworks

Fortunately, there is a lot of research done on writing multiple-choice questions with a high validity. Below you can find a summary from reading online material and papers that can be useful:

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Stem guidance

1. Don't begin stems with the phrase, "Which of the following is true (or false)?" or "Each of the following statements is correct EXCEPT."
2. Avoid including information that is irrelevant, extraneous and confusing. This will interfere with the accurate measurement of our learning objectives.
3. Avoid jargon and high language complexity.
4. Keep questions short, avoid long reading exercises.
5. Make sure there is one and only one correct option. Empirical evidence shows that questions that have multiple correct answers have a lower validity.
6. Write phrases in the test positively and avoid negative words. Empirical evidence shows that people often overlook the negative term and will get the item wrong for the wrong reason.
7. Use multiple-choice to measure high level thinking.
8. It is important to avoid bias by unintentionally placing particular groups of students at an unfair disadvantage

Options guidance

1. Avoid giving students clues to the correct answers. This will negatively impact the validity of the test. Avoid giving clues through the use of faulty grammatical construction.
2. Every option should reflect on specific idea or element of the relevant content and one cognitive task.
3. The content of an option should be independent of the other items. Keep the options mutually exclusive.
4. Avoid trick options, those which mislead or deceive the student into answering incorrectly.
5. For each item, consider the timing, grade appropriateness, difficulty level, potential sources of bias (cultural, gender, or geographical), and ease of translation. Make sure that item validity is not affected by factors that unnecessarily increase the difficulty of the item, such as unfamiliar or overly difficult vocabulary, grammar, directions, contexts, or stimulus materials
6. Use as many options as necessary, but recent research shows that 3-5 options is best, often 4 answers are used while 3 is often sufficient. Asking questions with a varying number of options is often perceived positively. If it is functional add the option, if not remove the option.
7. Have only one correct answer not multiple. Empirical research has shown that this makes the test harder and will interfere with proper measurement of the validity. You could consider multiple True/False questions as an alternative.
8. Order the options in a logical order if possible.
9. Make sure all (or sets) of the response options are parallel in length, level of complexity, and grammatical structure. Avoid the tendency to include more details or qualifications in the correct response, thus making it stand out. If the options are not parallel in length, please order the options short to long if at all possible.
10. Do not use words or phrases in the stem that are repeated in one of the response options and, therefore, act as a clue to the correct response.
11. Do NOT use "none of these" and "all of these" as response options.
12. Position the correct option so that it appears about the same number of times each possible position for a set of items.
13. Use plausible distractors; avoid illogical distractors
14. Incorporate common errors of students in distractors
15. Avoid technically phrased distractors

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16. Use familiar yet incorrect phrases as distractors
17. Use true statements that do not correctly answer the question
18. In principle avoid the use of humor when developing options (recent research suggests there is some benefits if used properly but more research is needed)
19. Avoid using *none of the above* or *all of the above*
20. Keep the options homogeneous in content.

Question template

The basic framework for a test should really be defined prior to instruction and should reflect the instructional and learning goals and objectives. But to create a strong test, no matter how short it may be, always start with a test blueprint. The blueprint lists the content topics and the cognitive tasks we like to test. We will use the following template to collect questions from the knowledge experts (we avoid the term Subject Matter Experts (SMEs) because in EHDEN this stands for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises). This template is available in SharePoint as an Excel file.

Question 1.			
Topic	<i>Describe the topic you are assessing, e.g. Standardized Vocabularies: Hierarchy</i>		
Cognitive Skill	<i>Remembering / Understanding / Applying / Analyzing / Evaluating / Creating</i>		
Options	Text	Score	Rationale
A.			
B.			
C.			
D			

The topic field is needed so we can see how many questions are on a specific topic and often made error is that there is improper balance of the tests per topics which negatively affects the learning objectives. The cognitive skills are an extension of Bloom’s taxonomy described earlier to better match the instructional field. The score determines which answer(s) are correct, the score needs to sum up to 1. The Rationale is added so this can be used in the Moodle question to provide feedback.

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Other Types of questions

Moodle contains other question types you could consider for your course assessment. They are summarized below with links to more information.

- [Calculated](#): offer a way to create individual numerical questions by the use of wildcards (i.e. you can use common variables names as **x** , **y** enclosed in curly braces to create the wildcards **{x}** and **{y}**) that are substituted with random values when the quiz is taken.
- [Simple Calculated](#): offer a way to create individual numerical questions whose response is the result of a numerical formula which contain variable numerical values by the use of wildcards (i.e. **{x}** , **{y}**) that are substituted with random values when the quiz is taken.
- [Drag and drop into text](#): A drag and drop question type where missing words have to be dragged into gaps in a paragraph of text.
- [Drag and drop markers](#): This question type allows students to drop markers onto an area on a background image. Drag and drop markers questions differ from [Drag and drop onto image question type](#) in that there are no predefined areas on the underlying image that are visible to the student.
- [Drag and drop onto image](#): This question type allows students to drag words, images or both from a list and drop them into pre-defined gaps on a base image.
- [Calculated Multichoice](#): These questions are like multichoice questions with the additional property that the elements to select can include formula results from numeric values that are selected randomly from a set when the quiz is taken. They use the same wildcards than Calculated questions and their wildcards can be shared with other Calculated multichoice or regular Calculated questions
- [Description](#): simply shows some text (and possibly graphics) without requiring an answer. It is more of a label than a question type.
- [Essay](#): provides the option of answering by uploading one or more files and/or entering text online.
- [Matching](#): have a content area and a list of names or statements which must be correctly matched against another list of names or statements.
- [Embedded Answers \(Cloze\)](#): Embedded answers (Cloze) questions consist of a passage of text (in Moodle format) that has various answers embedded within it, including multiple choice, short answers and numerical answers.
- [Random Short Answer Matching](#): From the student perspective, the Random Short-Answer Matching question looks just like a [Matching question](#). The difference is that the sub-questions are drawn randomly from the [Short Answer questions](#) in the current category (including or not subcategories from the current category)
- [Select missing words](#): This is very similar to the [Drag and drop into text](#) question type, but uses drop-down menus in the text instead of drag-boxes.
- [Short-Answer](#): In a short answer question, the student types in a word or phrase in response to a question (that may include an image).

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- [Numerical](#): From the student perspective, a numerical question looks just like a short-answer question. The difference is that numerical answers are allowed to have an accepted error.
- [True/False](#): A student is given only two choices for an answer in this kind of question: True or False. The question content can include an image or html code.
- [Third-party question types](#): Besides the standard [Question types](#) that are part of the core Moodle distribution, there are a number of [additional question type plugins](#) in [the plugins database](#)

OHDSI-IN-A-BOX

In EHDEN we have a unique opportunity to use the Virtual Machine Image developed in OHDSI. This so called OHDSI-IN-A-BOX is a windows environment that can host all the OHDSI tools, a CDM database, Simulated Source Data, manuals etc. In EHDEN we will use this extensively in our trainings and we will further improve and extend it. For example, it is used in the CDM and Vocabulary course to execute queries against the CDM and in the ETL course it is used for exercises in mapping data. If you think it is useful for your course, ask the Academy team for more information (use the forum).

CONCLUSION

This running document will provide the basis for the deliverables on educational materials: D4.4 Report on education and training material for the developed analytical tools (M18 and M48). It provides some initial guidance for the course development.

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